

Sound Generated by Two-Dimensional Vortex Motion near a Half-Plane

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Abstract

In this paper, firstly, definition of vorticity, vorticity equation and laws of vortex motion are introduced. Two-dimensional vortex motion is explored using complex variable methods. Secondly, the influence of solid boundaries and Green's function are discussed. Two-dimensional Green's function for half-plane is also discussed. Finally, the vortex surface interaction noise in two dimensions and the sound produced by vortex motion near a half-plane are presented.

Introduction

Vortex sound is the sound produced as a by-product of unsteady fluid motions. It is part of the more general subject of aerodynamic sound. Any mechanism that produces sound can actually be formulated as a problem of aerodynamic sound.

In this paper, the production of sound by unsteady motion of fluid near a solid boundary, a solid body of characteristic dimension ℓ is compact for waves of frequency ω provided that $\frac{\ell}{\lambda} \ll 1$. We have known that Green's function is solution of wave equation. How the sound can be estimated vortex motion by using Green's function.

1. Basic Equations and Definitions

1.1. Vorticity

If the motion of a fluid is described by a velocity vector field $\underline{v}(\underline{r}, t)$, then $\underline{\nabla} \times \underline{v}$ is defined as the vorticity $\underline{\zeta}(x, t)$, that is

$$\underline{\zeta}(x, t) = \text{curl } \underline{v} = \underline{\nabla} \times \underline{v}.$$

For two-dimensional motion, $\underline{\zeta} = \text{curl } \underline{v} = \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \hat{k} = \zeta \hat{k}$

1.2. Vorticity equation

The equation of motion for an incompressible fluid can be written in terms of the vorticity, we have

where the vorticity $\underline{\zeta} = \underline{\nabla} \times \underline{v}$ and $\underline{F} = -\underline{\nabla} \Omega$ is conservative force. If the fluid has constant density and we have

$$\frac{D\underline{\zeta}}{Dt} = (\underline{\zeta} \cdot \underline{\nabla}) \underline{v}.$$

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For two-dimensional motion $(\underline{\zeta} \cdot \nabla) \underline{v} = \underline{\zeta} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\hat{u}\hat{i} + \hat{v}\hat{j}) = 0$,

and hence, we have $\frac{D\underline{\zeta}}{Dt} = 0$.

1.3. Three laws of vortex motion

For the motion of an ideal barotropic fluid under the action of conservative external body forces, they can be expressed as follows:

- (i) Fluid particles originally free of vorticity remain free of vorticity.
- (ii) Fluid particles on a vortex line at any instant will be on vortex line at all subsequent times. Alternatively, it can be said that vortex lines and tubes move with the fluid.
- (iii) The strength of a vortex tube does not vary with time during the motion of the fluid.

1.4. Two-dimensional vortex motion

The velocity $\underline{q} = (u, v)$ in two-dimensional fluid motion, we shall suppose the fluid to be inviscid and take the fluid density, ρ , as constant, if in addition the motion is irrotational then the velocity potential, ϕ will exist and satisfy Laplace's equation, $\nabla^2 \phi = 0$.

For rotational or irrotational motion the continuity condition becomes

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (2)$$

which is the condition that $vdx - udy$ is a perfect differential of some function, ψ say.

Figure. 1

Therefore $d\psi = vdx - udy$, and we can write

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = v, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = -u. \quad \text{Where } \psi \text{ is called the stream function.}$$

Consider the rate at which liquid mass crosses a curve AB, defined as the flow across AB. If P(x, y) and Q(x + δx, y + δy) are two neighboring points on AB, PR and QR are parallel to the coordinate axes, then flow from right to left across PQ = flow across PR – flow across QR

$$= \rho(v\delta x - u\delta y) = \rho\delta\psi .$$

Therefore flow across AB from right to left = $\rho \int_A^B d\psi$

$$= \rho[\psi_B - \psi_A].$$

This property could be used as an alternative definition of ψ . It follows that if the flow across PQ is zero, PQ is along the line of flow or stream line at P and $d\psi = 0$.

Hence the stream lines are given by

$$\psi = \text{constant}, \tag{3}$$

and because of this fact ψ is called the Stream function.

The stream function, ψ exists in this form only for two-dimensional motion and its existence depends on the density, ρ , being constant. Its existence does not depend on the motion being irrotational, as does existence of the velocity potential ϕ .

The components of the vorticity $\underline{\zeta}$ are $\left(0, 0, \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial y^2}\right)$. If the motion is irrotational, ψ satisfies Laplace's equation $\nabla^2\psi = 0$ and we have form

$$u \hat{i} + v \hat{j} = -\nabla\phi = -\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \hat{i} - \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} \hat{j}, \text{ with } \nabla^2\phi = 0 .$$

2. The Influence of Solid Boundaries and Green’s Function

2.1. The influence of solid boundaries

We shall frame the present discussion in terms of the acoustic wave equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2\right)\phi = -q(\underline{x}, t) \tag{4}$$

for the velocity potential, but our conclusions will be applicable quite generally. This equation determines ϕ in terms of a specified source distribution $q(\underline{x}, t)$. In the absence of solid boundaries (in free space) the results of free-space Green’s function enable us to represent ϕ in the form

$$\phi(\underline{x}, t) = \int \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -q(\underline{y}, \tau) G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d^3y d\tau. \tag{5}$$

Here $G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau)$ is the free space Green's function

$$G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) = \frac{1}{4\pi|\underline{x} - \underline{y}|} \delta\left(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x} - \underline{y}|}{c_0}\right), \quad (6)$$

that is, $G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau)$ is the outgoing wave solution of

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2\right)G = \delta(\underline{x} - \underline{y})\delta(t - \tau), \quad \text{where } G = 0 \text{ for } t < \tau. \quad (7)$$

A similar representation involving surface distributions of dipoles and monopoles is obtained for ϕ when we attempt to solve (4) using Green's function (6) in the situation illustrated in Figure 2, where the source distribution $q(\underline{x}, t)$ is adjacent to a rigid boundary S on which the normal derivative $\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x_n} = 0$.

The Green's function for those problems, where the typical wavelength of the sound produced by the source distribution $q(\underline{x}, t)$ is large compared to one or more principal dimensions of the solid body S , is called **the compact Green's function**. To simplify the calculation of the compact Green's function, we use the Fourier integral formula

$$\delta(t - \tau) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega(t - \tau)} d\omega, \quad (8)$$

which expresses the δ function as a linear combination of time-harmonic oscillations of frequency ω . If we now put

$$G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) e^{-i\omega(t - \tau)} d\omega, \quad (9)$$

then the substitution of this and (8) into the Green's function equation (7) shows that, for each frequency ω , $\hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega)$ is the solution of

$$(\nabla^2 + \kappa_0^2)\hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) = \delta(\underline{x} - \underline{y}), \quad (10)$$

where $\kappa_0 = \frac{\omega}{c_0}$ is called the acoustic wave number. Sound of frequency ω has wavelength

$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\kappa_0}$. Thus, a solid body of characteristic dimension ℓ is compact for waves of frequency ω provided that

$$\frac{\ell}{\lambda} = \frac{k_0 \ell}{2\pi} \ll 1. \tag{11}$$

Figure. 2

2.2. Green’s function for the wave equation

Let us verify the general relation (9) between the Green’s functions $G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau)$ and $\hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega)$, respectively, for the wave equation and the inhomogeneous Helmholtz equation in the special case in which there are no solid boundaries. According to this formula we find, using the expression (5) for the free space Green’s function $\hat{G}$,

$$\begin{aligned} G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) &= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) e^{-i\omega(t-\tau)} d\omega, \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi^2 |\underline{x} - \underline{y}|} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega(t-\tau - \frac{|\underline{x}-\underline{y}|}{c_0})} d\omega = \frac{1}{4\pi |\underline{x} - \underline{y}|} \delta(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x} - \underline{y}|}{c_0}), \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

2.3. Green’s function for a half-plane

Analytical representations of the exact Green’s function $\hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega)$ are known for a rigid half-plane $x_1 < 0, x_2 = 0$ but are of limited use in applications. However, we can define a compact Green’s function for a source at $\underline{y}$ whose distance from the edge is small compared to the acoustic wavelength, that is, for $\kappa_0 (y_1^2 + y_2^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \ll 1$.

Figure. 3

To do this, we introduce cylindrical polar coordinates.

$$\underline{x} = (r \cos \theta, r \sin \theta, x_3), \quad \underline{y} = (r_0 \cos \theta_0, r_0 \sin \theta_0, y_3).$$

Then, if $\hat{i}_3$ is a unit vector in the x_3 direction (parallel to the edge),

$$\hat{G}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) = \hat{G}_0(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) + \hat{G}_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) + \dots, \tag{13}$$

where, for $|\underline{x} - y_3 \hat{i}_3| \rightarrow \infty$ and $\kappa_0 \sqrt{y_1^2 + y_2^2} \ll 1$,

$$\hat{G}_0(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) = -\frac{1}{4\pi |\underline{x} - y_3 \hat{i}_3|} e^{i\kappa_0 |\underline{x} - y_3 \hat{i}_3|},$$

$$\hat{G}_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, \omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi \sqrt{2\pi i}} \frac{\sqrt{\kappa_0} \phi^*(\underline{x}) \phi^*(\underline{y})}{|\underline{x} - y_3 \hat{i}_3|^{\frac{3}{2}}} e^{i\kappa_0 |\underline{x} - y_3 \hat{i}_3|} \tag{14}$$

and,
$$\phi^*(\underline{x}) = \sqrt{r} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad \phi^*(\underline{y}) = \sqrt{r_0} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_0}{2}\right). \tag{15}$$

$\phi^*(\underline{x})$ is a velocity potential of incompressible flow around the edge of the half-plane expressed in terms of polar coordinates $(x_1, x_2) = r(\cos \theta, \sin \theta)$ and similarly for $\phi^*(\underline{y})$. The component $\hat{G}_0$ of $\hat{G}$ represents the radiation from a point source at $\underline{y}$ when scattering is neglected; $\hat{G}_1$ is the first correction due to presence of the half-plane.

2.4. Two-dimensional Green's function for a half-plane

The Green's function for the wave equation in two dimensions, where conditions are uniform in the x_3 direction, satisfies

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) G = \delta(x_1 - y_1) \delta(x_2 - y_2) \delta(t - \tau), \quad \text{where } G = 0 \text{ for } t < \tau. \quad (16)$$

when a line source at $\underline{y} = (y_1, y_2)$ is close to the edge of the half-plane in Figure 2, the corresponding compact Green's function is obtained by integrating (11) over $-\infty < y_3 < \infty$, using the method of stationary phase for $\kappa_0 \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2} \rightarrow \infty$ and then using the formula (6) to calculate $G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \approx G_0(\underline{x}, t - \tau) + G_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) + \dots$.

In particular $G_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau)$ is the first term in the expansion that involves $\underline{y}$, and is found to be

$$G_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \approx \frac{\phi^*(\underline{x}) \phi^*(\underline{y})}{\pi |\underline{x}|} \delta\left(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}\right), \quad |\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (17)$$

where $\underline{x} = (x_1, x_2)$, $\underline{y} = (y_1, y_2)$ and ϕ^* is defined as in

2.5. Vortex sound at low Mach numbers

When the characteristic Mach number M is small the local mean values of the density and sound speed are related to their uniform respective values ρ_0 and c_0 at infinity by relations of the form

$$\frac{c}{c_0} \sim 1 + O(M^2), \quad \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \sim 1 + O(M^2).$$

The vortex sound equation can therefore be simplified by (a) taking $c = c_0$ and $\rho = \rho_0$, and (b) by neglecting nonlinear effects of propagation and the scattering of sound by the vorticity. The production of sound is then governed by the simpler equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) B = \text{div}(\underline{\omega} \times \underline{y}), \quad (18)$$

and in the far field the acoustic pressure is given by the linearized approximation

$$p(\underline{x}, t) \approx \rho_0 B(\underline{x}, t).$$

3. Sound Generated by vortex motion near a half-plane

3.1. Vortex- surface interaction noise at small Mach number

The small Mach number vortex sound equation (18) is now applied to determine the sound generated by vorticity in the neighborhood of a fixed body whose surface S may be vibrating at small amplitude.

Introduce a stationary, closed control surface S_+ on which $f(\underline{x})=0$, such that $f(\underline{x})\geq 0$ according as $\underline{x}$ lies without or within S_+ . The body is assumed to be within S_+ , and S_+ will subsequently be allowed to shrink down to coincide with the body surface S . Multiply (18) by $H\equiv H(f)$ and form the inhomogeneous wave equation for the new variable HB . We use the transformations

$$H\nabla^2 B = H \operatorname{div}(\underline{\nabla} B) = \operatorname{div}(H\underline{\nabla} B) - \underline{\nabla} H \cdot \underline{\nabla} B \quad (19)$$

$$= \nabla^2 (HB) - \operatorname{div}(B\underline{\nabla} H) - \underline{\nabla} H \cdot \underline{\nabla} B \quad (20)$$

and
$$H \operatorname{div}(\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) = \operatorname{div}(H\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) - \underline{\nabla} H \cdot \underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}.$$

Then (18) becomes

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) (HB) = -\operatorname{div}(B\underline{\nabla} H) - \underline{\nabla} H \cdot (\underline{\nabla} B + \underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) + \operatorname{div}(H\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}).$$

we can make the substitution

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\nabla} H \cdot (\underline{\nabla} B + \underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) &= -\underline{\nabla} H \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} + \underline{v} \operatorname{curl} \underline{\omega} \right) \\ &= -\underline{\nabla} H \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} + \underline{v} \operatorname{div}(\underline{\nabla} H \times \underline{\omega}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence the vortex sound equation becomes

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) (HB) = -\operatorname{div}(B\underline{\nabla} H) + \underline{\nabla} H \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}(H\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) - \underline{v} \operatorname{div}(\underline{\nabla} H \times \underline{\omega}) \quad (21)$$

The sources on the right of this equation are either concentrated on the control surface S_+ or lie in the fluid outside S_+ ; they completely determine B outside this control surface. The solution in this region can therefore be found by using any Green's function $G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau)$ that satisfies

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) G = \delta(\underline{x} - \underline{y}) \delta(t - \tau), \quad \text{where } G = 0 \text{ for } t < \tau$$

for $\underline{x}$ and $\underline{y}$ anywhere within the fluid. In Figure 4 the fluid occupies the region V outside the surface S of the solid body; the control surface

$S_+(f(x)=0)$ therefore lies within V . Thus, for points $\underline{x}$ within the fluid the solution of (21) is

$$HB(\underline{x}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_V G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \left\{ -\text{div}(\underline{B}\nabla H) + \nabla H \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial \tau} + \text{div}(\underline{H}\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}) - \nu \text{div}(\nabla H \times \underline{\omega}) \right\} d^3 \underline{y} d\tau,$$

Where all of the source terms within the brace brackets are functions of $\underline{y}$ and τ . Those involving ∇H vanish except on the control surface S_+ . The divergence terms are removed by application of the divergence theorem, and then using the formula.

Let us illustrate the procedure for the first term in the brace brackets of the integrand

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V G \{ -\text{div}(\underline{B}\nabla H) \} d^3 \underline{y} &= - \int_V \{ \text{div}(\underline{B}\nabla H) - \nabla H \cdot \underline{B} \} d^3 \underline{y} \\ &= \oint_{S+\Sigma} \underline{B}\nabla H \cdot d\underline{S} + \int_V \nabla H \cdot \underline{B} d^3 \underline{y} \\ &= 0 + \oint_{S_+} \underline{B}\nabla H \cdot d\underline{S} \\ &= \oint_{S_+} \underline{B}(\underline{y}, \tau) \frac{\partial G}{\partial y_n}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d\underline{S}(\underline{y}), \end{aligned}$$

where all vector operators are with respect to the $\underline{y}$ dependence, and Σ is a large, closed "surface at infinity" where $\underline{\omega} = 0$. There are no contributions from S and Σ because $\nabla H = 0$ everywhere except on S_+ . The general solution in the region $f > 0$ outside S_+ accordingly becomes

$$\begin{aligned} B(\underline{x}, t) &= \oint_{S_+} \left(\underline{B}(\underline{y}, \tau) \frac{\partial G}{\partial y_n}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) + G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \frac{\partial v_n}{\partial \tau}(\underline{y}, \tau) \right) d\underline{S}(\underline{y}) d\tau \\ &\quad - \int_V H(f(\underline{y})) (\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v})(\underline{y}, \tau) \cdot \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d^3 \underline{y} d\tau \\ &\quad + \nu \oint_{S_+} \underline{\omega}(\underline{y}, \tau) \times \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \cdot d\underline{S}(\underline{y}) d\tau, \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

where for brevity we have omitted the integration sign for τ which is understood to vary over the range $-\infty < \tau < \infty$. We now choose G to have vanishing normal derivative on the surface S of the body. When this is done the control surface S_+ is allowed to shrink down onto S , and the general solution in the fluid becomes

$$\begin{aligned} B(\underline{x}, t) &= - \int_V (\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v})(\underline{y}, \tau) \cdot \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d^3 \underline{y} d\tau \\ &\quad + \nu \oint_S \underline{\omega}(\underline{y}, \tau) \times \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \cdot d\underline{S}(\underline{y}) d\tau + \oint_S G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \frac{\partial v_n}{\partial \tau}(\underline{y}, \tau) d\underline{S}(\underline{y}) d\tau, \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where $\frac{\partial G}{\partial y_n}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) = 0$ on S .

Figure. 4

In the acoustic far field ($|\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty$) we can replace $B(\underline{x}, t)$ by $\frac{p(\underline{x}, t)}{\rho_0}$.

The contribution to the sound from surface fraction is nominally of order

$$\frac{1}{Re} \ll 1, \quad Re = \frac{v\ell}{\nu},$$

relative to the contribution from the volume vorticity, where ℓ is the characteristic length scale of the turbulence or body and v is a typical velocity. At high Reynolds numbers the surface term can therefore be discarded, and in the important case in which the body does not vibrate the acoustic far field is given by

$$\frac{p}{\rho_0}(\underline{x}, t) = - \int_V (\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v})(\underline{y}, \tau) \cdot \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d^3 \underline{y} d\tau. \tag{24}$$

3.2. Compact Green’s function in two dimensions

In this section we apply the general high Reynolds numbers solution (24) to determine sound produced by two-dimensional interactions of rectilinear vortices with a stationary solid boundary. We shall derive the two-dimensional analogue of the general solution

$$\frac{p}{\rho_0}(\underline{x}, t) = - \int_V (\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v})(\underline{y}, \tau) \cdot \frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) d^3 \underline{y} d\tau \tag{25}$$

by first determining a suitable representation of G in two dimensions. Both the vorticity convection velocity $\underline{v}$ and the Lamb vector $\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v}$ are parallel to the $x_1 x_2$ plane, so that only the y_1 and y_2 components of the gradient $\frac{\partial G}{\partial \underline{y}}$ contribute to the integral. Also, because

$(\underline{\omega} \times \underline{v})(\underline{y}, \tau)$ depends only on y_1, y_2 and τ , the integration with respect to the spanwise coordinate y_3 involves only the Green's function.

Let
$$G_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) dy_3. \tag{26}$$

For two-dimensional problems G is a function of $y_3 - x_3$, and the function G_2 will therefore satisfy the Green's function equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) G_2 = \delta(x_1 - y_1) \delta(x_2 - y_2) \delta(t - \tau), \text{ where } G_2 = 0, \text{ for } t < \tau, \tag{27}$$

obtained by integrating the three-dimensional equation (4) over $-\infty < y_3 < \infty$.

3.3. The trajectory of a line vortex adjacent to a rigid half- plane

Consider a line vortex of strength $\Gamma > 0$ adjacent to a rigid half-plane lying along the negative real axis $x_1 < 0, x_2 = 0$.

The transformation

$$\zeta = i\sqrt{z}, \quad z = x_1 + ix_2, \quad -\pi < \arg z < \pi, \tag{28}$$

maps the fluid region $-\pi < \arg z < \pi$ into the upper half $\text{Im}\zeta > 0$ of the ζ plane Figure 5(b).

Figure. 5

Let the vortex at $z_0(t)$ map into a vortex at $\zeta = \zeta_0(t)$. The velocity potential $w(\zeta)$ of the motion in the ζ plane is found by introducing an image vortex of strength $-\Gamma$ at $\zeta = \zeta_0^*(t)$, in which case

$$w = -\frac{i\Gamma}{2\pi} \ln(\zeta - \zeta_0) + \frac{i\Gamma}{2\pi} \ln(\zeta - \zeta_0^*).$$

In the z -plane this becomes

$$w(z) = -\frac{i\Gamma}{2\pi} \ln(\zeta(z) - \zeta(z_0)) + \frac{i\Gamma}{2\pi} \ln(\zeta(z) - \zeta^*(z_0)).$$

Let $z_0 = re^{i\theta}$. Then the real and imaginary parts of the equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx_{01}}{dt} &= \cos\theta \frac{dr}{dt} - r \sin\theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma}{8\pi r} \left(\sin\theta + \tan\frac{\theta}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{dx_{02}}{dt} = \sin\theta \frac{dr}{dt} + r \cos\theta \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dx_{02}}{dt} = -\frac{\Gamma}{8\pi r} (\cos\theta + 1).$$

Therefore, $\frac{dr}{dt} = -\frac{\Gamma}{8\pi r} \tan\frac{\theta}{2}$, $\frac{d\theta}{dt} = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi r^2}$

that is $r \frac{d\theta}{dr} = 2 \cot\frac{\theta}{2}$.

Thus, $r = \ell \sec\frac{\theta}{2}$, $\ell = \text{constant}$.

This is the polar equation of the trajectory plotted in Figure 6. The constant length ℓ is equal to the distance of the closet approach of the vortex to the edge of the half-plane, which occurs at $\theta = 0$. Substituting for r in the equation $\frac{d\theta}{dt} = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi r^2}$, we find

$$\sec^2\frac{\theta}{2} \frac{d\theta}{dt} = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi\ell^2}.$$

$$\frac{x_{01}}{\ell} = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}}, \quad \frac{x_{02}}{t} = \frac{-2\frac{Ut}{\ell}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}},$$

where $U = \frac{\Gamma}{8\pi\ell}$.

Thus, (for $\Gamma > 0$) the vortex starts above the half-plane at $t = -\infty$ at $x_{01} = -\infty$, $x_{02} = 2\ell$

and translates towards the edge, initially at speed U parallel to the plane. It crosses the x_1 axis at $t = 0$ at $x_{01} = \ell$, and proceeds along a symmetrical path below the half-plane.

Figure. 6

3.4. Sound produced by vortex motion near a half-plane

The trajectory of a line vortex of strength Γ interacting with a rigid half-plane is shown in Figure 6 for ideal motion at low Mach number. The sound generated by the vortex is calculated using the two-dimensional compact Green’s function (23), which can be written

$$G_1(\underline{x}, \underline{y}, t - \tau) \approx \frac{\phi^*(\underline{x})\phi^*(\underline{y})}{\pi\sqrt{|\underline{x}|}} \delta(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}), |\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty.$$

where $\phi^*(\underline{x}) = \sqrt{r} \sin(\frac{\theta}{2})$, $\phi^*(\underline{y}) = \sqrt{r_0} \sin(\frac{\theta_0}{2})$ and $\underline{x} = |\underline{x}|(\cos \theta, \sin \theta)$, the coordinate being defined as in Figure 6. This is applicable when the distance r_0 from the edge of the source at $(y_1, y_2) = r_0(\cos \theta, \sin \theta)$ is much smaller than the acoustic wavelength.

For a line vortex at (r_0, θ_0) , the characteristic frequency $\sim \frac{v}{r_0}$, where v is the vortex translational velocity. The wave length is therefore of order

$$\frac{r_0}{v} \times c_0 = \frac{r_0}{M} \gg r_0 \text{ for } M = \frac{v}{c_0} \ll 1,$$

so that low Mach number motion is sufficient to ensure that the wavelength of the sound is much larger than the vortex distance from the edge.

From (25)

$$\begin{aligned} p(\underline{x}, t) &\approx -\rho_0 \int \Gamma \underline{k} \times \frac{d\underline{x}_0}{dt}(t) \delta(\underline{x} - \underline{x}_0(t)) \underline{\nabla} \phi^*(\underline{y}) \frac{\sin \frac{\theta}{2}}{\pi\sqrt{|\underline{x}|}} \times \delta(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}) d^3 \underline{y} d\tau, \\ p(\underline{x}, t) &\approx \frac{-\rho_0 \Gamma \sin \frac{\theta}{2}}{\pi\sqrt{|\underline{x}|}} \int \underline{k} \times \frac{d\underline{x}_0}{d\tau}(\tau) \cdot \underline{\nabla} \phi^*(\underline{y}) \delta(\underline{y} - \underline{x}_0(\tau)) \times \delta(t - \tau - \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}) dy_1 dy_2 d\tau \\ &= \frac{-\rho_0 \Gamma \sin \frac{\theta}{2}}{\pi\sqrt{|\underline{x}|}} \left[\underline{k} \times \frac{d\underline{x}_0}{dt} \cdot \underline{\nabla} \phi^* \right], \quad |\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Figure. 7

Now ϕ^* is the velocity potential of an ideal flow around the edge of the half-plane in the anticlockwise sense (with streamlines as in Figure 6). It is the real part of the complex potential

$$w = \phi^* + i\psi^* = -i\sqrt{z}, \quad z = y_1 + iy_2,$$

where ϕ^* and the stream function ψ^* satisfy the Cauchy-Riemann equations

$$\frac{\partial \phi^*}{\partial y_1} = \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial y_2}, \quad \frac{\partial \phi^*}{\partial y_2} = -\frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial y_1}.$$

Since $\hat{k} \times \nabla \phi^* = \nabla \psi^*$.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{k} \times \frac{d\mathbf{x}_0}{dt} \cdot \nabla \phi^* &= -\frac{d\mathbf{x}_0}{dt} \times \hat{k} \cdot \nabla \phi^* = \frac{d\mathbf{x}_0}{dt} \cdot \hat{k} \times \nabla \phi^* \\ &= -\frac{d\mathbf{x}_0}{dt} \cdot \nabla \psi^*. \end{aligned}$$

The acoustic pressure can therefore be put in the form

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{x}, t) &\approx \frac{\rho_0 \Gamma \sin \frac{\theta}{2}}{\pi \sqrt{|\mathbf{x}|}} \left[\frac{d\mathbf{x}_0}{dt} \times \nabla \psi^* \right] \\ &= \frac{\rho_0 \Gamma \sin \frac{\theta}{2}}{\pi \sqrt{|\mathbf{x}|}} \left[\frac{D\psi^*}{Dt} \right], \quad |\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $\left[\frac{D\psi^*}{Dt} \right]$ is evaluated at the retarded position of the vortex.

The stream function ψ^* is constant on each of the parabolic streamlines of the ideal flow around the edge defined by ϕ^* , Figure 6. A vortex that translated along one of these streamlines would be silent; the actual edge-generated sound depends on the rate at which the trajectory of the vortex cuts across the streamlines of this ideal edge flow. This is found as follows:

$$\psi^* = -\sqrt{r_0} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_0}{2}\right).$$

Therefore,
$$\frac{D\psi^*}{Dt} = \frac{\partial\psi^*}{\partial r_0} \cdot \frac{dr_0}{dt} + \frac{\partial\psi^*}{\partial\theta_0} \cdot \frac{d\theta_0}{dt}$$

$$\frac{D\psi^*}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{r_0}} \frac{dr_0}{dt} \cos\frac{\theta_0}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{r_0}}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_0}{2}\right) \frac{d\theta_0}{dt},$$

where $r_0 = \ell \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}$, $\theta_0 = 2 \tan^{-1}\left(-\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)$ are given by (29) in which r is replaced by r_0 and θ is replaced by θ_0 . Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dr_0}{dt} &= \frac{\ell}{2\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}} \times 2 \frac{U^2 t}{\ell^2} \\ &= \frac{U^2 t}{\ell \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}} = \frac{\left(\frac{\Gamma}{8\pi\ell}\right)^2 \frac{t}{\ell}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Again, since $\tan \frac{\theta_0}{2} = -\frac{Ut}{\ell}$,

$$\sec^2 \frac{\theta_0}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\theta_0}{dt} = -\frac{U}{\ell},$$

$$\left[1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2\right] \frac{d\theta_0}{dt} = -\frac{2U}{\ell},$$

$$\frac{d\theta_0}{dt} = \frac{-\frac{2U}{\ell}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2\right]}.$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{D\psi^*}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{r_0}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \frac{\left(\frac{\Gamma}{8\pi\ell}\right)^2 \frac{t}{\ell}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2}} + \frac{\sqrt{r_0}}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\frac{-2\frac{U}{\ell}}{1 + \left(\frac{Ut}{\ell}\right)^2} \right], \quad |\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then we get

$$p(\underline{x}, t) \approx \frac{\rho_0 \Gamma^2}{(4\pi\ell)^2} \left(\frac{\ell}{|\underline{x}|} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\frac{\frac{\Gamma t}{8\pi\ell^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{\Gamma t}{8\pi\ell^2}\right)^{\frac{5}{4}}} \right]_{t \rightarrow \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}}, \quad |\underline{x}| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (30)$$

where ℓ is the distance of closest approach of the vortex to the edge (where it crosses the x_1 axis at time $t = 0$, in Figure 5.

Conclusion

The turbulence generated sound is equivalent to solving this equation for the radiation into a stationary, ideal fluid produced by a distribution of quadrupole sources whose strength per unit volume is the Lighthill stress tensor T_{ij} . The stream function ψ^* is constant on each of the parabolic streamlines of the ideal flow around the edge defined by ϕ^* , Figure 6. A vortex that translated along one of these streamlines would be silent; the actual edge-generated sound depends on the rate at which the trajectory of the vortex cuts across the streamlines of this ideal edge flow.

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